

Sol 2710 1 of 3

After driving up
on to the
pediment

Sol 2741 1 of 3

After driving down
off the pediment

Sol 2750 1 of 3

After arrival at
Glasgow drill site

Sol 2753 1 of 3

During drilling
at Glasgow

Sol 2762 1 of 3

At Glasgow drill site

Sol 2763 1 of 3

At Glasgow drill site

Sol 2764 1 of 3

At Glasgow drill site

Sol 2779 1 of 3

At Glasgow drill site

Sol 2781 1 of 3

Sol 2782 1 of 3

Sol 2783a 1 of 3

Pre-drive

Sol 2783b 1 of 3

Post-drive

Sol 2786 1 of 3

Sol 2787 1 of 3

Sol 2788a 1 of 3

Pre-drive

Sol 2788b 1 of 3

Post-drive

Sol 2790a 1 of 3

Pre-drive

Sol 2790b 1 of 3

Post-drive

Sol 2793a 1 of 3

Pre-drive

Sol 2793b 1 of 3

Post-drive

Sol 2795 1 of 3

Sol 2796 1 of 3

Sol 2797 1 of 3

Sol 2798 1 of 3

Sol 2800 1 of 3

Sol 2802 1 of 3

Sol 2804a 1 of 3

Sol 2804b 1 of 3

Sol 2816 1 of 3

Sol 2817 1 of 3

Sol 2820 1 of 3

Sol 2822 1 of 3

Sol 2824 1 of 3

Sol 2830 1 of 3

Sol 2843 1 of 3

Sol 2856 1 of 3

Sol 2866 1 of 3

Sol 2873 1 of 3

Sol 2878 1 of 3

Sol 2889 1 of 3

Sol 2905 1 of 3

Sol 2913 1 of 3

Sol 2923 1 of 3

Sol 2924 1 of 3

Sol 2927 1 of 3

Sol 2929 1 of 3

Sol 2931 1 of 3

Sol 2933 1 of 3

Sol 2936 1 of 3

Sol 2938 1 of 3

Sol 2940 1 of 3

Sol 2943 1 of 3

Sol 2947 1 of 3

Sol 2950 1 of 3

Sol 2958a 1 of 3

Sol 2958b 1 of 3

Sol 2965a 1 of 3

Sol 2965b 1 of 3

Sol 2967a 1 of 3

Sol 2967b 1 of 3

Sol 2970 1 of 3

Sol 2972a 1 of 3

Sol 2972b 1 of 3

Sol 2974 1 of 3

Sol 2977a 1 of 3

Sol 2977b 1 of 3

Sol 2991 1 of 3

Sol 2995 1 of 3

Sol 2998 1 of 3

Sol 3000 1 of 3

Sol 3020 1 of 3

Sol 3025 1 of 3

Sol 3026 1 of 3

Sol 3032 1 of 3

Sol 3033 1 of 3

Sol 3038a 1 of 3

Sol 3038b 1 of 3

Sol 3040 1 of 3

Sol 3045 1 of 3

Sol 3047 1 of 3

Sol 30xx 1 of 3

Sol 30xx 1 of 3

Sol 2710 2 of 3

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Sol 2787 2 of 3

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Pre-drive

Sol 2790b 2 of 3

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Post-drive

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Sol 2796 2 of 3

Sol 2797 2 of 3

Sol 2798 2 of 3

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Sol 2804b 2 of 3

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Sol 2817 2 of 3

Sol 2820 2 of 3

Sol 2822 2 of 3

Sol 2824 2 of 3

Sol 2830 2 of 3

Sol 2843 2 of 3

Sol 2856 2 of 3

Sol 2866 2 of 3

Sol 2873 2 of 3

Sol 2878 2 of 3

Sol 2889 2 of 3

Sol 2905 2 of 3

Sol 2913 2 of 3

Sol 2923 2 of 3

Sol 2924 2 of 3

Sol 2927 2 of 3

Sol 2929 2 of 3

Sol 2931 2 of 3

Sol 2933 2 of 3

Sol 2936 2 of 3

Sol 2938 2 of 3

Sol 2940 2 of 3

Sol 2943 2 of 3

Sol 2947 2 of 3

Sol 2950 2 of 3

Sol 2958a 2 of 3

Sol 2958b 2 of 3

Sol 2965a 2 of 3

Sol 2965b 2 of 3

Sol 2967a 2 of 3

Sol 2967b 2 of 3

Sol 2970 2 of 3

Sol 2972a 2 of 3

Sol 2972b 2 of 3

Sol 2974 2 of 3

Sol 2977a 2 of 3

Sol 2977b 2 of 3

Sol 2991 2 of 3

Sol 2995 2 of 3

Sol 2998 2 of 3

Sol 3000 2 of 3

Sol 3020 2 of 3

Sol 3025 2 of 3

Sol 3026 2 of 3

Sol 3032 2 of 3

Sol 3033 2 of 3

Sol 3038a 2 of 3

Sol 3038b 2 of 3

Sol 3040 2 of 3

Sol 3045 2 of 3

Sol 3047 2 of 3

Sol 30xx 2 of 3

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At Glasgow drill site

Sol 2764 3 of 3

At Glasgow drill site

Sol 2779 3 of 3

At Glasgow drill site

Sol 2781 3 of 3

Sol 2782 3 of 3

? (Probably)

Sol 2783a 3 of 3

Pre-drive

Sol 2783b 3 of 3

Post-drive

Sol 2786 3 of 3

Sol 2787 3 of 3

Sol 2788a 3 of 3

Pre-drive

Sol 2788b 3 of 3

Post-drive

Sol 2790a 3 of 3

Pre-drive

Sol 2790b 3 of 3

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